

What is saved? Considerations on documenting, archiving and (re-)performing computer music

Miriam Akkermann

TU Dresden

Miriam.akkermann@tu-dresden.de

ABSTRACT

The importance of valuable strategies for archiving computer music works becomes more and more obvious, as technology rapidly changes. Besides the challenges caused by the digital technologies, ranging from compatibility problems to the question of how to store the work's data, the strategies of saving information concerning the works, as well as the goals of documenting and archiving can be quite divers. In this article, a cycle of documentation, archiving and re-performance is proposed and discussed based on theoretical approaches and in combination with archiving strategies and their possible goals.

1. INTRODUCTION

When working on the issue of archiving computer music, many challenges discussed are connected to the rapidly developing (digital) technologies. Very prominent challenges are e.g. the short live cycles of technical equipment, compatibility-problems that appear between technological generations, and the task of transferring (technical) information from one engineer to another, and between engineers and musicians. In addition, archiving music always has to take into account questions concerning a performance: Is there enough information to either replay (e.g. from recordings) or re-perform the piece (– if it is a work that was meant to be audible for an audience)?

When looking at preservation or archiving projects, it becomes obvious that there exists a mutual influence between documentation, archiving and re-performances of musical works. Central questions hereby are: Which information should be archived? How? And for what purpose/performance tradition? For computer music and mixed music, also technical questions appear: How can the code be kept working? Which format should be used? How to deal with hardware systems? And in terms of sustainability: How can digital data be stored in order to provide long lasting archives with accessible data?

When aiming at a systematic structure along which a documentation is done, a major question also is: Who decides what information concerning the composition and its performance is documented – and therefore will be archived? And, in consequence: What is accessible for future performances?

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Implicitly, these thoughts are closely connected to the well-known debate on performance practice, as well as to interpretative decisions. The notations of 1980s mixed music works e.g. provide not only incomplete information on set-up and presets of the original hardware, they often also lack playing instructions for the electronics, or contain notes which were not made for use during a performance.

The accessibility of information on how to perform a composition, however, can be essential for the future existence of these works. On the one hand, a piece can be buried in oblivion as nobody knows how to perform it. On the other hand, a lack of interest regarding re-performances can cause also a lack of interest in establishing a long-term preservation of still existing information.

Documentation, archiving and (re-)performance of a composition therefore share knowledge and information within an abstract interactive system, which is strongly depend and related to former and future content. In this paper, this interrelationship is outlined as ‘cycle of documentation, archiving and re-performance’, and discussed based on theoretical approaches deriving from Suzanne Briet as well as observed along archiving goals.

2. DOCUMENTING, ARCHIVING, (RE-)PERFORMING

The assumption that information changes over time depending on its documentation and archiving is already known from many music genres. In computer music, change and accessibility of information is directly linked to fast technological developments and quick changes of digital generations. This causes challenges for long-term archiving as discussed e.g. by Serge Lemouton and Samuel Goldszmidt, showing also a “Cycle de vie des versions”, in which they formalized the documentation process and the interlaced genesis of different versions of a composition’s available sources in context of Sidney, a data base at IRCAM. [1] In addition, a slightly more general cycle of documentation, archiving and re-performance can be proposed, allowing the observation of basic knowledge transfer and transformation within a clearly definable setting.

Figure 1. Basic cycle of documentation, archiving and re-performance.

2.1 Basic sources

In music, compositions are usually expected to be taken down by score and composer's note, optionally accompanied by performance instructions and a legend to the used symbols. In computer music, also code, programs, circuit plans and set-up descriptions are common. Besides the challenge of (precise) notation¹, also the question on documentation of a work, including the decision on what additional information should be kept in this documentation in order to properly contour the musical work, becomes more and more evident.

Librarian Suzanne Briet describes in her treatise *Qu'est-ce que la documentation* [2], which was published already in 1951, a discussion on the definition of 'documentation'. She describes connected tasks and challenges, as well as a classification system that she developed for documenting. Amongst others, there are three aspects Briet discusses, which are especially interesting in the context of computer music: the definition of the content which is considered to be 'the document', the necessity to deal with technologies and suitable techniques, and the fact, that she sees documentation as a 'cultural technique', which is embedded in a social and cultural (historically grown) framework [2]. This last aspect is commonly important for analytical and historical observations, and often discussed concerning the performance practice, but yet hardly emphasized in context of archiving or preserving music. Ronald E. Day, who co-translated Briet's treatise from French to English, explicitly accentuates in his introduction, that Briet demands from someone who is in charge of documenting to be able to consider both, the work in its whole context, and "documents as assuming varieties of physical forms and formats [3]".

The challenges and tasks described by Briet already in the 1950s concerning systematizing the process of documentation are currently still discussed. The thoughts on digital archiving and the challenges rising for example with the idea of a digital histography have been in debate for almost ten years. At the same time, the pressure to come up with sensible technical and archival solutions for long term preservation increases, as e.g. the live span of many technical devices from the 1980s and 1990s comes towards an end. This closely goes together with the observation, that the information on computer music works derives from in-between the disciplines provided by composers, performers, music practitioners, sound engineers, musicologists and computer scientists. In all these related fields, there exist well-constructed approaches and ideas to work on emerging challenges, usually linked to very pragmatic problems, such as saving (archiving) or (re-)performing existing compositions or analytical tasks. Deliberating these interwoven challenges based on theoretical concepts can help to assign these different approaches onto more general structures and reveal recurrent processes. Briet's thoughts on 'documentation' offer a possible theoretical outline.

When transferring her approach to music, this implies that the original sources would consist of information

concerning the work as well as its social and cultural framework. This framework can be established e.g. by information on composer, performer and technician, host institution, the premiere's location and audience, and performance habits, but it can also be outlined by information on the work's genesis and the process of establishing the premiere. One approach that provides such insights in the genesis of compositions was presented by Guillaume Boutard and Fabrice Marandola. Focusing on the compositional process with live electronics, they followed the composer while developing the composition and its premiere, including also eventual changes and further developments during this process in their documentation. For this, they proposed a multiple methods approach, following the idea of collecting "several kinds of traces of the activity during the creative processes (observation videos, sketches, annotations, diagrams, notes, and so on) [4]", and accompanied this with methods of confrontation. Boutard and Marandola propose a method mix which provides a profound information package with a focus that is clearly set on the ideas of the composer.

As a major goal of this project, Boutard and Marandola mention dissemination [4]. In terms of Briet, they define what they want to document, they face the challenge of the ephemeral technologies by their method mix, and offer information concerning social and cultural context. At the same time, this approach externalizes knowledge transfers, which have been restricted to oral tradition, such as information on performance habits / performance practice, and the use of technology within musical performances. Compared to the information on traditional music works, this creates a quite different set of source material, which can help to keep re-performances of compositions not necessarily more similar, but closer to the composer's ideas. Conversely, composer, performer, as well as researcher have to be aware that with this approach, they create the basic source material for a composition, and simultaneously become 'documentalists' along Briet's definition [2], when creating a composition, or establishing or reporting from a premiere.

2.2 Documentation approaches and their goals

Decisions on the documentation of a composition and its premiere shape the source material – and therefore strongly influence not only the available information, but also the retrospective appearance of a work as well as its future presentation. These decisions are usually taken depending on the documentalist's goals. The intention with which a documentation is processed, however, can be quite divers: Briet discusses the influence of selection on the "[d]ocumentary unity [which] tends to get close to the elementary idea [...] [and the process of documenting] as 'a cultural technique' of a new type [2]" as separate but equally important aspects. She also emphasizes the pros, cons and challenges of different documentation strategies. Despite this, most other approaches show strong tendencies concerning the goal of their documentation. Boutard's and Marandola's approach clearly focuses on the

¹ The term 'notation' refers in this paper to standardized and non-standardized ways of conveying compositional content in musical context. It includes e.g. graphical scores, text, and computer programs.

composer and his artistic process of establishing the composition [4]. The main interest of Susan MacDonald, in contrast, is set on the audiences' impression [5].

MacDonald, who specialized on conservation, aims at recreating the phenomenon of the art work in order to provide the audience with the same impressions as the 'original artwork'. In her concept, she refers to two approaches: Suzanne Briet's idea of a document as a complex array of signs within "a social and technological framework, existing in multiple forms to meet multiple needs [5]"; and Simon Tanner, who combines the information management metaphor of *container*, *content* and *context* with Briet's idea of the *information container*, and uses this as basis for discussing challenges of digital preservation and web archives [4, 5]. MacDonald combines these two approaches, and classifies the *container* as 'the pointer' that connects the information with associated actions, taking place in a certain cultural and technological framework [5]. When following this argumentation, the question comes up, if (and to what extent) a documentation can incorporate adequate information on *container*, *content* and *context*. How can the *context* be outlined e.g. in a documentation of a musical work so that the *content* 'points' in a suitable direction? MacDonald's approach implies, that the appearance of an artwork can change within a certain range that is created by the interplay of *content*, *container* and *context* in order to be able to recreate the aspired impressions.

In both cases – when focusing on the composer and his artistic ideas, and when aiming at the audience's impression –, the documentation of a work contains the very basic source material, the (musical) art work itself (in traditional or explained fixation), as well as additional information, e.g. on context, inherent ideas or the framework that seems necessary to create a (re-)presentation of the work which serves the intended goal: a (re-)performance of the work along the composer's ideas, or an impression that comes close to the one evoked by the original work.

When transferring MacDonald's terminology on computer music, there are appear several possible assignments: the score can be seen as *content* which is provided using the *container*, e.g. a performance format or the knowledge on performance habits at a specific moment in time and a specific location, considering the *context*, e.g. the work's cultural context or the circumstances under which the composer created the work. It is, however, also possible to rate the direct surrounding cultural environment as well as the available technology as *context*, and information such as presets or the use of the electronics – which may not be explicitly provided by a score – as *container*. This can help to deal with the fact that artistic ideas and technical (digital) achievements have often been developed in close relationship, as the work can be examined within various possible view points and also according to the technical framework. This approach includes, however, already strong interpretational decisions. MacDonald emphasizes that her interest is to offer the audience a congruent impression of an artwork. This aspired impression usually derives from knowledge on the work but is also influenced by curatorial decisions, especially, as the challenge remains to present an impression that evokes a corresponding audience's experience. As the cultural and technological framework has altered over time, a composition can cause a completely

different experience for today's audience, even when providing aesthetic impressions that are close to the ones shown at the premiere. Or a composer may have lowered his sights at the premiere due to technical restrictions – and may therefore not completely have intended the impression at the premiere but wishes to change that for future performances. The guidelines for a work's impression can therefore be influenced by various motives, and the decisions taken during the documentation of a work's re-performance therefore go hand in hand with the selection process for archiving, shaping the work's prospective source material.

2.3 Archiving and preserving

Joshua Sternfeld claims in his explanation on 'Digital Histography' that all systems of digital preservation "share the same objective, that is, they all use digital technology to represent history [7]". He states that archival processes are the key to the contextualization of the preserved objects, which he calls 'units of historical information', as those has passed "a selection process, a search inquiry, and archival provenance [7]". In other words, the archived information reflects the understanding of historiography as well as the archival perspective of the person in charge of archiving. Sternfeld focuses in his remarks not only on originally digital content but any information that is archived in using current digital technologies.

This approach implies that the technology used for archiving may also change the initial information and that additional steps are necessary to unfold the archived information. In computer music, this process can be well observed when looking at programs or patches of compositions. Even though existing in digital formats from the very beginning, code creates major challenges for archiving which are directly linked to the archiving technology: if code is bound to hardware, it may have to be extracted and ported (again and again) to newer versions in order to run on other but newer devices. This usually means that there are several code versions that enter the archiving system. Is the goal of an archive to keep information on a composition in order to perform the piece, updated versions may replace the original code in the documentation over time. The original source material 'code' is 'overwritten', as recent technology can neither archive nor access it. The archival process provides the necessary contextualization with which the preserved objects can be reclassified. The archival process as Sternfeld puts it, provides information on the work and becomes at the same time *content* as well as *container*, 'pointing' from *content* to associated actions.

On the one hand, the documentation includes the resulting elements of a performance which add to the already existing archived source material; on the other hand, information may implicitly get lost through archival selection processes. At the same time, it becomes obvious that a complete preservation of the whole original material connected to a composition and its premiere is, at least in the field of computer music, almost impossible. This leads to seemingly incomplete states of source material, depending on the goal with which the information is retrieved from the archive. Musicological questions and practical performative challenges, for example, often request quite different information structures and 'units of historical

information'. This raises the question, at what set of source material a work is considered to be 'well preserved'.

Sternfeld addresses this question from a theoretical side in accentuating that it is necessary to distinguish between 'records' and 'documents' in order to withdraw evidence from information. 'Records' preserve, following Sternfeld who refers to Luciana Duranti and Kenneth Thibodeau [8], "the context surrounding its creation and transactional history; [this] embodies more than the information contained within its documentary form [7]". Interestingly, this definition of 'records' corresponds on a systematic level to MacDonald's approach of documentation and conservation. [6] This assumption is encouraged by Sternfeld, who emphasizes that the archived information and its collocation within the archiving system is equally important but that both entities are interdependent and interactive [7].

2.4 Re-performance and its documentation

A main goal for archiving music compositions is usually to provide sufficient and substantial information based on which it is possible to develop a re-performance of a work. As outlined above, documentation and archiving can be established with different aims, but while most of the classical (analog) music performances are (explicitly or implicitly) embedded in ongoing debates on (historically informed) performance practice, many of the upcoming performances in computer music seem to find themselves primarily caught in debates on technical issues. This suggests that in computer music, the technical sources are strongly related to performance issues, which in consequence means that each technical framework is interlinked to a particular performance practice – a fact that should be reflected also in the documentation. Possible solutions for this challenge are as various as the underlying documentation and archiving strategies and goals. Sparse sources can cause thereby positive and negative effects: On one side, the re-performance may change due to decisions which were not intended originally by the composer (and which will enter directly in the ongoing documentation process), on the other side, there opens up a creative freedom concerning the criteria for artistic decisions within this process of preparing the re-performance.

This directly entails two questions: How can or should a re-performing process be documented? And, how do this re-performance and the premiere relate to each other? The first question can be related to Kevin Dahan's approach of acknowledging reconstruction of works as preservation strategy, which to him includes already information on strategies of how to present the related artifact in an up-to-date environment [9]. As Dahan looks also at electroacoustic works, reconstruction does hereby not necessarily mean re-performance, but can be also considered as such, depending on the genre of the musical work. This also goes well together with the aspect, that the future existence of a musical work can be linked to an interest in its performance. The second question brings up philological issues, but also touches the debate on authenticity and authentic performance. At the same time, it closes the 'cycle of documentation, archiving and re-performance' in – literally and in terms of MacDonald – pointing back to the process of documentation. In deciphering the archived sources and selecting information from the documented material as

relevant for the re-performance, the examination of the sources is in full progress. If a (re-)performance in the end matches the criteria for authenticity depends also on the goal of the re-performance.

3. CONCLUSION

The outlined 'cycle of documentation, archiving and re-performance' provides an abstract structure for a quite well-known challenge, relating to both, the practical procedure of documentation and archiving processes, as well as to archival theories. In deliberating this cycle based on theoretical concepts it is possible to retrace and reveal inherent (possibly existing) biases across involved disciplines in order to better understand ongoing strategies on archiving computer music and electro-acoustic music. The outlined considerations can provide basis for an analytical observation of current and ongoing archiving projects, which have been left out in this paper.

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